

Table 2. N response and agronomic N-use efficiency of different rice varieties.

Variety	Response function ^a	R ²	Optimum N dose (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield at optimum N dose (t ha ⁻¹)	Agronomic N-use efficiency (kg ha ⁻¹)
<i>Shallow submergence (15-25 cm)</i>					
CST7-1	Y = 3492 + 11.45 x - 0.0165x ²	0.874	48.0	4.0	10.62
IR16294-CS-9-1	Y = 2563 + 10.84 x - 0.0160x ²	0.847	44.7	3.4	12.01
C200-BS-6-23	Y = 2845 + 09.57 x - 0.0175x ²	0.887	38.0	3.2	8.95
CSRC(S)5-2-25	Y = 2562 + 09.43 x - 0.0142x ²	0.871	34.0	2.9	9.11
CSRC(S)14-1-B-0	Y = 2895 + 09.85 x - 0.0147x ²	0.900	36.5	3.2	9.31
CSRC(S)11-4-4-1	Y = 3165 + 10.15 x - 0.0131x ²	0.815	41.6	3.6	9.85
<i>Semideep submergence (25-50 cm)</i>					
C300-BD-50-11	Y = 2840 + 09.67 x - 0.0175x ²	0.801	25.7	3.1	9.73
C99-BD-9-26	Y = 2685 + 09.75 x - 1.0157x ²	0.811	34.0	3.0	9.41
CSRC(D)4-3-0	Y = 2705 + 10.51 x - 0.0178x ²	0.890	37.6	3.1	9.84
CSRC(D)13-12-2-1	Y = 2512 + 09.14 x - 0.0185x ²	0.847	36.7	3.1	9.26
C340-22-5	Y = 2125 + 10.52 x - 0.0114x ²	0.878	26.6	2.4	10.34
C340-22-17	Y = 2401 + 09.65 x - 0.0100x ²	0.844	28.0	2.7	9.64

^aY in kg ha⁻¹.

Influence of organic, biofertilizer, and inorganic forms of nitrogen on rice quality

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We studied the complementary effect of organic and inorganic N along with biological N sources (*Azospirillum*) on rice quality. A field experiment with dry-season (kuruvai) rice (June-September) was conducted in 1996 and 1997.

Forty-five-day-old daincha (*Sesbania aculeata*) at 12 t ha⁻¹ and sunn hemp (*Crotalaria juncea*) at 11 t ha⁻¹ were incorporated *in situ* 3 d before rice transplanting. Farmyard manure was applied at 12.5 t ha⁻¹ at the start of first puddling. Rice was inoculated with *Azospirillum* through seed treatment (600 g ha⁻¹), seedling dip (100 g ha⁻¹), and soil application (200 g ha⁻¹). Considering the recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer of 150-50-50 kg NPK ha⁻¹, various proportions of mineral N (50%, 75%, and 100% of recommended N) were applied to account for the complementary effect of N from organic and biofertilizer forms.

Proper N nutrition and favorable soil conditions due to organic fertilizers and biofertilizers ensured the nutrient supply to the crop and improved the quality of rice grain. Incorporation of organic fertilizers and inoculation of *Azospirillum* along with application of inorganic N significantly increased optimum cooking time, lowered gruel loss, and improved total amylose and crude protein contents (see table). Among the organic fertilizers, daincha enhanced the quality characters

of rice best. Elongation ratio, however, was not influenced by the treatments. Incorporation of daincha at 12 t ha⁻¹ and application of 50% of recommended inorganic N plus *Azospirillum* inoculation improved rice quality.

Effect of N management on quality of rice^a.

Treatment	Optimum cooking time (min)	Elongation ratio	Gruel loss (%)	Total amylose content (%)	Crude protein (%)
<i>Organic fertilizers</i>					
M ₁ = control	14.6	1.41	3.9	25.2	7.8
M ₂ = FYM	16.2	1.42	3.6	26.4	8.3
M ₃ = daincha	17.2	1.46	3.1	28.4	9.2
M ₄ = sunn hemp	16.7	1.45	3.3	27.2	8.3
SE	0.3	0.03	0.06	0.3	0.13
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.7	ns	0.15	0.8	0.31
<i>Inorganic and biofertilizers</i>					
S ₁ = 50% N	14.4	1.42	3.1	24.9	7.8
S ₂ = 75% N	15.1	1.43	3.6	25.7	8.1
S ₃ = 100% N	16.0	1.44	4.1	26.6	8.5
S ₄ = 50% N + Azos	16.9	1.46	2.9	28.6	9.3
S ₅ = 75% N + Azos	17.2	1.46	3.4	27.8	8.9
S ₆ = 100% N + Azos	17.5	1.44	3.9	27.0	8.6
SE	0.32	0.04	0.05	0.31	0.11
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.65	ns	0.11	0.64	0.23

^aN = nitrogen, Azos = *Azospirillum*, FYM = farmyard manure, SE = standard error, LSD = least significant differences, ns = not significant.